

Driving towards disaster?

An empirical analysis of the factors that influence ZEV adoption in the UK

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Abstract

The UK Government intends for zero emission vehicles (ZEVs) to be the only fuel type of new vehicles that are purchased nationally by 2035. In this context, this study examines the current level of ZEV adoption rates and analyses the factors that could influence these rates using various regression models with data from the last 10 years. The results of this paper suggest that the two key policies that the UK Government should utilise to guarantee that this 2035 target is achieved are (1) to increase taxes on fuel prices and (2) ensure that there is an adequate public charging infrastructure across the country.

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1 Introduction

The UK Government targets having 100% of all new vehicles registered be zero emission vehicles (ZEVs) by 2035 (Department for Transport, 2023e). ZEVs produce no carbon dioxide when driven and are powered by batteries or fuel cells (Department for Transport, 2022b). Climate change is a growing UK issue, with annual mean temperatures increasing by over 1 degree centigrade from 1982 to 2022 (Met Office, 2022). Therefore, this goal aims to reduce carbon emissions and help the UK become 'net zero' by 2050 (HM Government, 2021).

However, Kampman et al. (2011) suggest that individuals rarely consider the environmental impacts when purchasing vehicles, which leads to an externality problem with an underconsumption of electric vehicles. Hence, government intervention may be necessary to achieve this target.

This paper intends to examine the relative importance of factors, on both the demand and supply side, that impact ZEV adoption rates in the UK. ZEVs made up just 13.8% of all new vehicles registered in Q2 2023 so a large increase in adoption rates is still required to reach this 2035 target (Department for Transport, 2023c). Therefore, it is important to determine if there is causality between ZEV adoption rates and certain factors, as this will affect the nature of government intervention (should it be necessary).

As discussed, most individuals make their vehicle purchasing decision based on financial rather than environmental factors (Kampman et al., 2011). Hence, an individual may consider the initial purchase cost of vehicles, fuel prices, electricity prices, and incentives, including tax breaks and subsidies.

Unquantifiable and non-financial factors, such as environmental morality, should also be considered. In 2023, a UK survey suggested that 87% of adults had altered their lifestyle to combat the climate crisis (Office for National Statistics, 2023). This implies that more consumers are making environmentally conscious purchasing decisions, which contradicts the theory proposed by Kampman et al. (2011). Therefore, the environmental impact of

vehicles may be a factor of growing importance. However, the incomes of consumers can be a barrier to purchasing ZEVs, particularly if upfront costs are high (Hardman et al., 2021).

Infrastructure can also be important. In July 2023 there were only 44,020 public ZEV chargers in the UK which clearly limits the number of ZEVs that can be purchased (Department for Transport, 2023a). There are also sizeable information gaps about ZEVs as this market is still relatively new. For instance, the range of vehicles, availability of charging points, and ease of refuelling are all key concerns (Krishna, 2021). Therefore, consumer perceptions may improve as time progresses and the market size increases. Correspondingly, adoption rates could increase without any changes to vehicle ownership costs.

As discussed, this target is highly ambitious. However, in the last 5 years ZEV adoption rates have increased dramatically by over 20 times, as illustrated by Figure 1. This may suggest reduced information gaps and improved consumer perceptions of ZEVs.

Figure 1: Proportion of cars registered per quarter in the UK that are ZEVs from Q1 2013 to Q2 2023

Source: Department for Transport (2023c)

The UK is not the only country to have set aggressive ZEV targets. For instance, all EU countries aim to achieve a 100% ZEV share of all new vehicle sales by 2035 at the latest (The International Council on Clean Transportation, 2024). In general, many characteristics of the UK, including demography and infrastructure, are similar to numerous other European countries, particularly those in Western Europe (Wolfe, 2017). Hence, analysing the progress of these European countries will provide a strong idea of how successful the UK has been at encouraging ZEV adoption.

Table 1: Target dates for 100% of new vehicles sold to be ZEVs across Europe

Year of 100% target	Countries
2025	Norway
2030	Austria, Denmark, Greece, Iceland, Netherlands,
2035	UK, Belgium, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Italy, Sweden

Sources: Department for Transport (2023c), Norwegian Public Roads Administration (2024) and The International Council on Clean Transportation (2024)

Table 1 shows that Norway have set a very assertive target of 2025. In January 2024 91.2% of all new cars were ZEVs in Norway (Norwegian Public Roads Administration, 2024). Hence, Norway will likely achieve this target. Countries such as Austria and Denmark have also set more aggressive targets than the UK. Figure 2 provides an overview of ZEV adoption rates across Europe.

Figure 2: Proportion of vehicles registered as ZEVs across European countries in 2022

Sources: Department for Transport (2023c), European Environment Agency (2023) and Norwegian Public Roads Administration (2024)

Figure 2 demonstrates that Nordic countries have been the most progressive in encouraging ZEV adoption with Norway the clear frontrunner. Sweden and Iceland have the next best ZEV adoption rates. Based on comparisons with the policies of other European countries it is evident that Norway has been successful for two key reasons. Firstly, Norway has world-leading charging infrastructure across the country, with 8 times the number of ZEV chargers per capita than the EU average (Wallbox, 2021). Secondly, Norway's incentive schemes have been hugely effective, with the standout policy being the removal of VAT on the upfront cost of ZEVs (Norsk elbilforening, 2023). This has generated a far lower relative price of ZEVs than most grants used to subsidise vehicles in countries such as the UK (Wallbox, 2021).

In general, adoption rates are below 20% in most countries. Hence, vast growth is required for most countries to achieve their targets. The UK is in a

fairly positive position with one of the highest adoption rates across Europe. It is particularly encouraging that the UK is ahead of some countries with 2030 targets, such as Austria and Greece, and marginally trail others such as Denmark and the Netherlands.

This paper will use various regression models to determine the causal impact of multiple variables on ZEV adoption rates in the UK. The results of this paper argue that increasing both taxation on fuel prices and the supply of public ZEV chargers are the key government policies to ensure that this 2035 target is achieved.

This paper is structured with Section 2 analysing previous literature on the topic. Section 3 focuses on the data and methodology, with Section 4 examining the results. Section 5 assesses the potential implications of these results for the UK Government. Section 6 concludes the findings of this paper.

2 Literature Review

A large quantity of literature analyses the impact of various factors on electric vehicle adoption rates. In particular, much of this literature involves empirical studies across a number of countries. Currently there is a minimal number of studies that focus directly on the UK. Therefore, it will be interesting to compare this literature with the results of this paper.

This review is separated into 6 factors that all impact electric vehicle adoption rates according to the literature. These factors are (1) fuel prices and their relationship with electricity prices, (2) the initial cost of vehicles, (3) government incentives, (4) consumer preferences, (5) the supply of public ZEV chargers, and (6) income. Although these factors have been separated, there are many links between them which will be discussed.

2.1. Fuel and electricity prices

The literature suggests that fuel and electricity prices, which are both direct costs of vehicle ownership, impact electric vehicle adoption rates. In general, it is expected that an increase in fuel prices or reduction in electricity prices would increase the demand for electric vehicles.

Empirical studies from Barla, Couture and Samano (2016) as well as Leard, Linn and McConnell (2017) on Quebec and the United States respectively find that greater fuel prices will increase the adoption of more fuel-efficient vehicles such as ZEVs. Barla, Couture and Samano (2016) determined that whilst small price variations had little impact on adoption rates, a sharp alteration in prices led to substantial changes. Their data suggested that electric vehicle demand was quite strongly inelastic following a change in fuel prices, with a 1% increase in fuel prices resulting in a 0.3% increase in electric vehicle registration. By comparison, Narassimhan and Johnson (2014), who carried out a similar study in the United States using panel data regression, found that electric vehicle adoption rates were far more sensitive to fuel price

changes (i.e., more elastic). Their data suggested that a 1% increase in fuel prices resulted in over a 2% increase in electric vehicle adoption rates.

Moreover, Leard, Linn and McConnell (2017) argue that individuals are more responsive to increases in fuel prices than decreases. This is rational as increases in fuel prices will negatively impact the budget constraint of a household, potentially making them reconsider their vehicle options. By comparison, owning a petrol or diesel vehicle is currently the norm. Hence, consumers are likely to be less reactionary to decreasing fuel prices. However, they also suggest that if fuel prices have been consistently high for a long period of time, an additional increase will have a lower marginal impact on electric vehicle adoption rates than expected (i.e., stronger price inelasticity at this level). This is potentially because many of the individuals who have not already switched to an electric vehicle by this point are also driven by non-financial factors, such as concerns about charging electric vehicles, which may offset any financial benefits from switching to an electric vehicle when fuel prices are increased further. Furthermore, high fuel prices will add pressure to household budgets which may prevent them from having the adequate funds to purchase an electric vehicle. Therefore, the impact of fuel prices may depend on the magnitude of the change in prices, the direction of the change (increasing or decreasing), and the initial price that it changes from.

Furthermore, Bushnell, Muehlegger and Rapson (2022) carried out empirical research in California analysing the impact of both fuel and electricity prices. Their data suggested that increasing fuel prices or decreasing electricity prices will positively impact electric vehicle adoption rates. However, they concluded that fuel prices are far more influential than electricity prices on electric vehicle demand (greater price elasticity). They argue that one key reason for this is that fuel prices are noticed far more regularly than electricity prices. This is rational as fuel prices are seen on multiple occasions every time an individual drives when they pass a petrol station. By contrast, an individual may only notice changes to electricity prices when looking at their monthly household bill.

2.2. Initial cost of vehicles

The initial cost of vehicles massively impacts the vehicle purchasing decision. For instance, Fridstrøm and Østli (2021) carried out a study in Norway from 2002 to 2016, which determined that electric cars are price elastic with a magnitude of 1.27. Hence, a decrease in the initial cost of the vehicle will generate a sizeable increase in demand. This is supported by Kampman et al. (2011), who argue that the cost of electric vehicles can be a significant barrier to entry in EU countries as they tend to be more expensive than other vehicles. They also suggest that individuals seldom contemplate the environmental impact of vehicles in their purchasing decision. Therefore, until technology improves, and the cost of electric vehicles falls (which they expect to happen in the long run), adoption rates will be low.

In addition, technology improvements may lead to a continuous cycle, as increases in electric vehicle sales may create economies of scale for manufacturers, which will reduce the average production costs for vehicles, allowing them to be sold at lower prices (Sperling, 1996). Hence, the relative price of electric vehicles would fall further.

Moreover, Cooke (2021) suggests that without adequate financing it is difficult for low or even middle-income households to afford new electric vehicles. This not only caps the electric vehicle market but also has knock-on effects on other factors. For example, without a sizeable market information gaps and uncertainty about using electric vehicles may persist. This emphasises the significance of income levels on electric vehicle adoption rates.

2.3. Government incentives

Government policies can incentivise individuals to purchase and use electric vehicles, as well as disincentivise individuals from using petrol and diesel cars. Financial factors such as fuel prices and the initial cost of vehicles can have a huge impact on electric vehicle demand. Hence, government policies can target these areas.

For instance, Holland et al. (2016), who carried out empirical research on the USA, suggest that to encourage electric vehicle adoption, the government could either introduce a subsidy (discount upfront cost) on electric vehicles or impose a tax (increasing fuel prices) onto driving petrol and diesel vehicles. Their research determined that imposing a tax on the number of miles driven by petrol and diesel vehicles was far more effective than introducing a subsidy on electric vehicles. This is potentially because individuals are more reactionary and inclined to switch vehicles when impacted by a disincentive of higher fuel prices, which affects their current consumption of petrol or diesel vehicles, than the incentive of lower initial electric vehicle costs. This is supported by the theory proposed by Leard, Linn and McConnell (2017) in Section 2.2, which argues that consumers are more sensitive to increases in the lifetime costs of petrol or diesel vehicles than decreases.

However, studies from Rapson and Muehlegger (2021) as well as Clinton and Steinberg (2019) argue that subsidies are extremely important in increasing electric vehicle adoption rates. This is logical, as the evidence from Fridstrøm and Østli (2021) argued that electric vehicles are price elastic. Hence, a direct reduction in electric vehicle prices should encourage more consumers to purchase electric vehicles. Gong, Ardeshiri and Hossein Rashidi (2020) support these results following a study of over 1,000 individuals in New South Wales, Australia. Their data suggested that a subsidy on initial vehicle costs was the most important incentive to increase electric vehicle adoption, particularly amongst high income individuals, who were almost 4 times more likely to purchase electric vehicles when the discount was increased from AU\$3,000 to AU\$10,000. Smaller incentives such as removing parking fees had a minimal impact in this study. Therefore, significant incentives are necessary to change the decision of consumers.

Furthermore, Rapson and Muehlegger (2021) note that the environmental impact of increasing electric vehicle adoption rates is heavily dependent on how electricity is generated regionally. The study by Holland et al. (2016) also argues that externalities vary geographically. For instance, if electricity is generated by fossil fuels, an increase in the amount of electricity used when

an individual converts to an electric vehicle could negatively impact the environment, offsetting the environmental benefits from switching vehicles (and potentially exceed these benefits) (Holland et al., 2016). However, if electricity is generated by renewable energy, the environmental benefit from switching will be greater. In the latter case there will be a larger externality problem as the social benefits of electric vehicle adoption are higher in these areas. Therefore, it is important that the magnitude of these incentives is set accordingly in each area as a one-size-fits-all policy may not be as effective (Rapson and Muehlegger, 2021).

2.4. Consumer preferences

Consumer preferences are also a key determinant on the demand for electric vehicles. For instance, He et al. (2022) carried out a consumer survey in China and argue that purchasing an electric vehicle is both an emotional and financial decision. They suggest that the environmental morality of consumers and desire to reduce emissions are key driving forces behind these emotional decisions. However, in certain cases, particularly amongst high income individuals, they argue that this decision is influenced by how this vehicle purchase will be perceived by others. This is supported by Buhmann and Criado (2023), who argue that the reputation of an individual is the key emotional variable that determines their vehicle purchasing decision.

Furthermore, Egbue and Long (2012) found that consumers are often overconcerned about factors that could affect their utility of driving. For example, they determined that 87% of the individuals studied globally averaged a daily mileage of below 40 miles, which is significantly lower than the range of most electric vehicles. Hence, this should not be as sizeable an issue as it is currently perceived to be. The time to refuel is also another key consideration for consumers, given that the average ZEV takes at least 15 minutes to recharge in the UK (Department for Transport, 2021).

These points emphasise the importance of educating individuals about electric vehicles. This would stress the environmental importance of electric

vehicles and remove any apprehensiveness that consumers have about purchasing them. In general, better educated individuals are likely to have more awareness about the impacts of vehicles on climate change, which may make them more inclined to purchase electric vehicles (Michael et al., 2022).

Moreover, information gaps may prevent many consumers from purchasing electric vehicles. Hence, early adopters are necessary to increase the awareness and visibility of electric vehicles within the market (Krishna, 2021). This can result in continuous growth in adoption rates as more people will be encouraged to purchase electric vehicles as many of the initial concerns that they had will be diminished over time.

2.5. Supply of public ZEV chargers

The supply of public electric vehicle chargers can also affect electric vehicle demand and reduce information gaps. For instance, a low number of public chargers can restrict the demand for electric vehicles as consumers do not feel that there is an adequate infrastructure level to utilise electric vehicles effectively (Krishna, 2021). This is supported by Sommer and Vance (2021), whose research calculated that each additional charger that was built in Germany generated a monthly increase of 0.062 in the number of electric vehicles registered (0.273 in rapid chargers). However, it could be argued that charging infrastructure is being increased accordingly over time to meet demand for electric vehicles, rather than being a constant constraint. Hence, the impact of the number of chargers may be less severe than anticipated.

2.6. Income

Income is also an important factor. In general, electric vehicles are more popular amongst high income individuals (Hardman et al., 2021). One reason for this is that the initial cost of electric vehicles is a significant barrier to entry (Cooke, 2021). One potential solution to this, which is often omitted in the literature, is a favourable credit scheme for electric vehicle purchases.

Furthermore, information gaps, which generate concerns about factors such as vehicle range, are another reason for greater adoption rates amongst high income individuals (Egbue and Long, 2012). Individuals with higher incomes are more likely to have the facilities to charge their vehicles at home (Hardman et al, 2021). Hence, this would reduce many concerns about the range and time to refuel vehicles as there is less reliance on public chargers. Furthermore, high income individuals are more likely to have more than one vehicle (Hardman et al, 2021). Therefore, an electric vehicle may not necessarily be the main vehicle in their household, which further reduces any apprehension about the range of electric vehicles, such as making long journeys (Krishna, 2021).

Higher incomes can also be driven by high education levels (Heckman, Humphries and Veramendi, 2018). Hence, higher income earners may prefer to purchase electric vehicles as they are more conscious of the environmental impacts that their vehicle purchase decision has (Michael et al., 2022).

The theory of higher incomes generating greater electric vehicle adoption rates is supported by a study by Xue et al (2021). When examining 20 countries across the world they calculated that the number of electric vehicles registered rose by 2.157% following a 1% increase in income levels. Therefore, electric vehicle adoption rates can be very sensitive to an increase in income.

3 Data

3.1. Methodology

This paper aims to determine the impact that various factors have on the adoption rates of ZEVs in the UK using regression analysis. The dependent variable is the proportion of cars registered every month that are ZEVs. This data was collected from the Department for Transport (2023c) and covers a time period of January 2013 to June 2023. However, this data is initially non-stationary, so a transformation is required.

Similar studies have used a variety of different approaches to transform and examine this data, with the most common being linear, logistic, negative binomial and Poisson regression models (Soltani-Sobh et al., 2017; Lane et al., 2018; Selena Sheng et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2023). These four models were all considered for this analysis. However, a large part of this data is underdispersed, with the mean consistently larger than the variance.

Therefore, both the negative binomial and Poisson regression models cannot be used (Harris, Yang and Hardin, 2012; Payne et al., 2015; Yang and Berdine, 2015). Hence, two models can be used to analyse this data:

1. Ordinary least squares (OLS) linear regression: data transformed by taking the natural log of the dependent variable.
2. Logistic regression: calculate and take the natural logarithm of the odds ratio of the dependent variable over time (Sperandei, 2014).

The various regressors, which account for all six factors, will be discussed in more detail below.

3.2. Contributing factors

There are a number of independent variables in this analysis. It is important that all of the potential factors that can influence ZEV adoption are represented in some capacity. Hence, the data collection process and variables can be separated into the various factors that were discussed in Section 2.

3.2.1. Fuel and electricity prices

The literature review suggested that either an increase in fuel prices or decrease in electricity prices, which will reduce the relative lifetime cost of owning a ZEV, will increase electric vehicle adoption rates (Narassimhan and Johnson, 2014; Bushnell, Muehlegger and Rapson, 2022). Hence, fuel and electricity price indices were collected from the Department for Energy Security and Net Zero (2023) for this analysis. The specific variable that will be examined is the difference between fuel and electricity price indices every month. It is expected that an increase in the difference between fuel and electricity price indices will increase ZEV adoption rates.

3.2.2. Initial cost of vehicles

The next factor to consider is the initial cost of vehicles. Data on the price of petrol, diesel, electric and alternatively fuelled vehicles was collected from the Auto Trader Group (2023) Retail Price Index for this variable. The variable that will be investigated is the relative price of electric vehicles compared to the rest of the market. Based on the literature it can be anticipated that a reduction in the relative price of electric vehicles will generate greater ZEV adoption rates (Kampman et al. 2011; Fridstrøm and Østli, 2021).

3.2.3. Government incentives

Specific government incentives are also important to consider. This can be separated into two variables.

Firstly, the plug-in car grant, which was introduced by the UK Government in 2011, has been used to reduce the upfront cost of ZEVs (Department for Transport, 2022a). Hence, the variable studied for this analysis will be the size of the government grant over time. This data was collected from Carwow (2022). It is expected that larger subsidies will encourage ZEV adoption rates to rise (Clinton and Steinberg, 2019; Rapson and Muehlegger, 2021; Gong, Ardeshiri and Hossein Rashidi, 2020).

Secondly, altering taxes can incentivise electric vehicle adoption (Holland et al., 2016). For example, road taxes for ZEVs have been kept lower than for equivalent vehicles with alternative fuel types. This will lower the lifetime cost of ZEVs relative to other vehicles. Therefore, the variable examined will be the average road tax savings for a ZEV, which was sourced from the HM Government (2017). Leibling (2008) suggests that most cars are owned for approximately 3 years before being sold. Hence, average tax savings will be calculated across a time period of 3 years. It is expected that greater tax savings will increase ZEV adoption rates.

3.2.4. Consumer preferences

There are a number of variables that can be used to represent consumer preferences.

The first variable that will be examined is the monthly recycling level in the UK, which was collected from the Environment Agency (2023). This variable is beneficial for this analysis as it can be a key indicator of the environmental consciousness of consumers. Recycling is currently available to all individuals in the UK, and it is their personal choice, based on their environmental morality, whether to recycle or not. Hence, the environmental morality of

individuals, which was discussed as a key influence on electric vehicle adoption rates by He et al. (2022) and Buhmann and Criado (2023), can be analysed using this measure. In general, environmental morality is difficult to quantify, and without appropriate surveys over an adequate period of time, this is currently the most quantifiable data that can represent this variable. It is anticipated that a larger recycling level would represent a greater consideration of the environmental impacts of a purchasing decision, resulting in greater ZEV adoption rates.

The range of electric vehicles can also influence electric vehicle adoption rates (Egbue and Long, 2012). The most accurate data is from Ritchie (2023), who sourced their data from the US Environmental Protection Agency on the average range of electric vehicle models over time. Although this dataset is from the USA, the majority of electric vehicle models in this study are available in both the USA and the UK, so this remains an accurate representation of electric vehicle ranges over time in the UK. It would be expected that ZEV adoption rates will increase as their range increases.

The final variable for consumer preferences is education. As argued by Michael et al. (2022), greater education levels reduce information gaps which can prevent consumers from purchasing electric vehicles. Data was collected from Stats Wales (2023), which provided information on the percentage of the working population in the UK that had at least level 2 qualifications over time (i.e., GCSE or equivalent). Greater education levels may provide individuals with more information or awareness about electric vehicles which could increase ZEV adoption rates. Higher education can also be associated with greater income levels which can improve adoption rates further (Heckman, Humphries and Veramendi, 2018; Hardman et al, 2021).

3.2.5. Supply of public ZEV chargers

The supply of public ZEV chargers is also an important factor as it can significantly limit the demand for electric vehicles (Krishna, 2021; Sommer and Vance, 2021). The variable that will be analysed is the total number of public electric vehicle chargers across the UK each month. This data was collected from the Department for Transport (2023b). It is clear that an increase in the quantity of chargers would be expected to generate greater ZEV adoption rates.

3.2.6. Income

Income can also impact ZEV adoption rates. The first variable to examine is the income index, which was sourced from the Office for National Statistics (2024a) and demonstrates the average monthly income across the UK. Given the studies from Kampman et al. (2011), Cooke (2021), as well as Hardman et al. (2021), it can be anticipated that a greater income index will increase ZEV adoption rates.

Furthermore, unemployment rates should be considered. A study from Meyer (2016) suggests that unemployed individuals are less inclined to make environmentally beneficial purchases. Hence, greater unemployment rates should result in lower ZEV adoption rates. This data was collected from the Office for National Statistics (2024b) which accounts for the monthly UK unemployment rate over time.

A variable for credit availability was also considered. However, this data was difficult to source and appropriately quantify for this specific study.

Nonetheless, data to represent this variable would be beneficial in future studies.

3.2.7. Summary statistics

This data, which covers a time period of January 2013 to June 2023 (126 observations), is summarised in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Summary statistics of data for regression analysis

Variable	Count	Mean	Median	SD	Max	Min
Dependent Variable						
Proportion of cars registered as ZEVs	126	0.047	0.01	0.070	0.32	0.00
Independent Variables						
1. Fuel and electricity prices						
Fuel and electricity index difference	126	-41.984	-35.80	29.403	-1.50	-132.60
2. Initial cost of vehicles						
Relative prices of electric vehicles	126	1.363	1.36	0.256	1.96	0.92
3. Government incentives						
Subsidies on upfront cost (£)	126	3642.857	4500.00	1554.165	5000.00	0.00
Tax breaks (£)	126	670.487	649.42	65.910	763.04	452.11
4. Consumer preferences						
Recycling (1,000 kg)	126	621.217	622.98	53.174	741.09	492.34
Range of electric vehicles (miles)	126	156.524	125.00	70.995	247.00	84.00
Education (%)	126	80.014	79.30	3.394	88.20	75.50
5. Supply of public ZEV chargers						
Number of public chargers (1,000s)	126	5.680	2.64	5.900	24.41	0.10
6. Income						
Income index	126	0.557	0.60	2.033	7.20	-4.00
Unemployment rate (%)	126	4.883	4.52	1.195	7.97	3.50

All of these variables will be considered when running a regression for both model 1 (OLS regression with natural log transformation) and model 2 (logistic regression). Hence, the general regression equation for both models in this analysis is:

Proportion of cars registered monthly which are ZEVs

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \alpha + \beta_1 (\text{fuel index} - \text{elec index}) + \beta_2 \text{relative prices} \\
 &+ \beta_3 \text{subsidies} + \beta_4 \text{tax break} + \beta_5 \text{recycling} + \beta_6 \text{range} \\
 &+ \beta_7 \text{education} + \beta_8 \text{chargers} + \beta_9 \text{income} + \beta_{10} \text{unemployment} \\
 &+ e
 \end{aligned}$$

Where α represents the intercept and e represents the error variable. This is the key regression equation for the data analysis.

4 Results

4.1. Initial regression

The initial results from this data analysis are expressed below.

Table 3: Results from initial regression analysis

Variables	(1) OLS with ln(ZEV)	(2) Logistic
1. Fuel and electricity prices		
Fuel and electricity index difference	0.0103** (0.0046)	0.0110** (0.0048)
2. Initial cost of vehicles		
Relative prices of electric vehicles	-0.0487 (0.4200)	-0.0784 (0.4390)
3. Government incentives		
Subsidies on upfront cost (£)	0.0004** (0.0002)	0.0004** (0.0002)
Tax breaks (£)	-0.0052*** (0.0010)	-0.0058*** (0.0010)
4. Consumer preferences		
Recycling (1,000 kg)	-0.0001 (0.0012)	-0.0002 (0.0000)
Range of electric vehicles (miles)	0.0154*** (0.0018)	0.0159*** (0.0019)
Education (%)	0.1602** (0.0635)	0.1612** (0.0664)
5. Supply of public ZEV chargers		
Number of public chargers (1,000s)	0.0962*** (0.0359)	0.0972*** (0.0000)
6. Income		
Income index	0.0340 (0.0344)	0.0315 (0.0360)
Unemployment rate (%)	-0.3267*** (0.1015)	-0.3350*** (0.1061)
R Square	0.9442	0.9435
Adjusted R Square	0.9394	0.9386
Observations	126	126
Standard error in parentheses		
Statistical significance: * = p < 0.1, ** = p < 0.05, *** = p < 0.01		

When initially analysing the results of this regression in Table 3 it becomes clear that both models provide almost identical results. In fact, each variable has the same general effect (positive or negative) on adoption rates of ZEVs regardless of the model. Each variable also has the same level of statistical significance across models. Therefore, as both models provide extremely

similar results, model 1 will be the focus of this analysis, as this data is more straightforward to interpret and apply to the current ZEV adoption rates in the UK (Hellevik, 2009).

In general, the value of the adjusted R squared is very large (0.9394), which suggests that the variables calculated in this analysis account for most of the variance in ZEV adoption rates. Furthermore, most factors impact ZEV adoption rates as expected according to the literature, with the exception of tax breaks and recycling. Moreover, this data covers a time period where ZEV adoption rates were initially very low. Hence, the magnitude of the impacts of many variables may be over inflated in comparison to their relative impact on adoption rates now.

4.1.1. Fuel and electricity prices

The first factor to analyse is fuel and electricity indices. The data suggests that a 1 unit increase in the difference between fuel and electricity indices will generate a 1.03% increase in the proportion of cars registered that are ZEVs every month. This is statistically significant to the 5% level. This is a relatively large change per unit, given the vast variation (value of 864.536) in this variable over time as demonstrated by Table 3. Hence, this could be a variable for the UK Government to exploit should they wish to increase ZEV adoption rates.

4.1.2. Initial cost of vehicles

The next factor to investigate is the initial cost of vehicles. This matches the literature as the data suggests that a one unit increase in the relative price of electric vehicles will decrease ZEV adoption rates by 4.87%. However, this data is statistically insignificant. Furthermore, the magnitude of the change in adoption rates is far lower than expected following a sizeable increase in relative prices. One reason for this could be that subsidies were particularly high in 2013, and have gradually decreased over time (Carwow, 2022). The

rationale for this may have been to encourage the early adoption of ZEVs. Therefore, the data for the relative price of vehicles may be distorted as excessive subsidies in the early part of this time period reduced the disparity between the price of ZEVs and other vehicles much more than they do now.

4.1.3. Government incentives

The impact of government incentives also provides interesting results. For instance, an additional subsidy of £100 on the initial cost of vehicles should increase ZEV adoption rates by 4%. This is a considerable change and statistically significant at the 5% level. This is encouraging for the UK Government as it suggests that subsidies have previously been effective. However, these subsidies were set at particularly high levels at the start of this time period in order to encourage early adoption and have been gradually reduced over time. Hence, their impact, as demonstrated in the data, is likely to be larger than the outcome that would be expected if they were reintroduced. This is because many of the additional benefits that early adoption generates, such as huge increases in education and trust of ZEVs, will no longer be as effective. Therefore, subsidies could be considered by the UK Government but may not yield the results that the data suggests that they will.

Moreover, the data contradicts the literature by suggesting that for every extra £1 of tax breaks, ZEV adoption rates would be anticipated to fall by 0.52%. This is also statistically significant at the 1% level. However, one explanation for this is that other variables are far more crucial to a vehicle purchasing decision. For instance, Table 3 demonstrates that the maximum value of subsidies reached a magnitude of £5,000, whereas tax breaks only just exceeded £750. Hence, although consumers appreciate tax breaks, this is unlikely to be the key determinant between purchasing a ZEV and another vehicle. This matches the research by Gong, Ardeshiri and Hossein Rashidi (2020), as discussed in Section 2.3, which argued that significant incentives are necessary to change the vehicle purchasing decision of consumers.

Therefore, if tax breaks were set to similar levels as in Norway, they may have a more serious and potentially causal impact on adoption rates.

4.1.4. Customer preferences

The variables for customer preferences produce both encouraging and unexpected results. Firstly, the data contradicts the literature by suggesting that an increase in recycling levels will reduce the ZEV adoption rate. However, this variable was only used to represent environmental morality, which is difficult to quantify, and may differ from smaller measures, such as recycling, to larger measures, such as vehicle purchases. Hence, there may only be a weak relationship between recycling and ZEV adoption rates. This data is also statistically insignificant.

By contrast, the data on the impact of the range of electric vehicles provides encouraging results, suggesting that ZEV adoption rates increase by 1.54% for every additional mile of range. This is also statistically significant to the 1% level.

Furthermore, the impact of education generated positive results. According to the data, a rise in the percentage of the working population that had achieved at least level 2 qualifications by a value of 1% would generate a 16.02% rise in ZEV adoption rates. This is a significant change. However, as demonstrated by Table 3, there is only so much more room for growth in this variable, given that it has reached a maximum level of 88.20%. In addition, this variable is only an estimate of how environmentally knowledgeable consumers are regarding vehicle purchasing decisions. Hence, the impact of this variable may be lower than the data suggests.

4.1.5. Supply of public ZEV chargers

Perhaps the most interesting data is the impact of the number of public ZEV chargers. The data suggests that for every 1,000 additional charging points

installed ZEV adoption rates will increase by 9.62% at the 1% significance level. This is a massive impact and crucially one that can be impacted directly by the UK Government by increasing spending on charging infrastructure.

4.1.6. Income

Finally, the effect of income can be investigated. Firstly, the income index is estimated to generate a 3.4% increase in ZEV adoption rates for every unit increase in the index, which is a relatively small change given the variance (value of 4.133) demonstrated in Table 3. Furthermore, this is not statistically significant.

However, the data estimates that unemployment is impactful and statistically significant to the 1% level. For instance, the data demonstrates that for every fall in the unemployment rate by a value of 1% the ZEV adoption rate would be expected to increase by 32.67%. This is a significant change in adoption rates, although the unemployment rate is at a level of 4.3% as of June 2023 and hasn't gone below 3.5% in the last 10 years as demonstrated by Table 3. Therefore, this variable is limited in the future positive impact that it can have on adoption rates.

4.2. Robustness checks

To analyse these factors further, robustness tests will be carried out with 6 different models. Each model will be run using the same OLS regression as in Section 4.1 but will only contain the variables for 5 of the 6 factors discussed. Hence, fuel and electricity prices will be removed from model 1, the initial cost of vehicles will be removed from model 2, government incentives will be removed from model 3, customer preferences will be removed from model 4, the supply of ZEV chargers will be removed from model 5 and income will be removed from model 6. Therefore, the impact of each individual factor can be examined in more detail. The results are demonstrated below.

Table 4: Robustness checks

Variables	(1) No Factor 1	(2) No Factor 2	(3) No Factor 3	(4) No Factor 4	(5) No Factor 5	(6) No Factor 6
1. Fuel and electricity prices						
Fuel and electricity index difference		0.0102** (0.0044)	0.0089* (0.0051)	0.0011 (0.0055)	0.0057 (0.0043)	0.0119*** (0.0040)
2. Initial cost of vehicles						
Relative prices of electric vehicles	0.1923 (0.4133)		-0.3409 (0.4173)	1.3497*** (0.4310)	0.1094 (0.4268)	-1.2143*** (0.2315)
3. Government incentives						
Subsidies on upfront cost (£)	0.0004** (0.0002)	0.0004*** (0.0002)		-0.0002 (0.0002)	0.0002 (0.0002)	0.0002 (0.0002)
Tax breaks (£)	-0.0050*** (0.0010)	-0.0052*** (0.0010)		-0.0023* (0.0012)	-0.0063*** (0.0009)	-0.0047*** (0.0010)
4. Consumer preferences						
Recycling (1,000 kg)	-0.0006 (0.0012)	-0.0001 (0.0012)	0.0000 (0.0013)		-0.0008 (0.0012)	0.0001 (0.0012)
Range of electric vehicles (miles)	0.0149*** (0.0018)	0.0153*** (0.0015)	0.0118*** (0.0019)		0.0146*** (0.0018)	0.0183*** (0.0014)
Education (%)	0.1251** (0.0627)	0.1628*** (0.0592)	0.0192 (0.0551)		0.1821*** (0.0647)	0.1249* (0.0646)
5. Supply of ZEV chargers						
Number of public chargers (1,000s)	0.0655* (0.0338)	0.0956*** (0.0354)	0.1442*** (0.0331)	0.0443 (0.0441)		0.1099*** (0.0317)
6. Income						
Income index	0.0757** (0.0296)	0.0354 (0.0322)	0.0418 (0.0385)	0.2152*** (0.0344)	0.0823*** (0.0301)	
Unemployment rate (%)	-0.3237*** (0.1032)	-0.3361*** (0.0604)	-0.1711 (0.1060)	-0.6154*** (0.1181)	-0.3274*** (0.1041)	
R Square	0.9418	0.9442	0.9283	0.9046	0.9407	0.9390
Adjusted R Square	0.9372	0.9399	0.9234	0.8990	0.9361	0.9348
Observations	126	126	126	126	126	126
Standard error in parentheses						
Statistical significance: * = p < 0.1, ** = p < 0.05, *** = p < 0.01						

Overall, Table 4 demonstrates that the value of the adjusted R squared does not change significantly when a single factor is removed. In fact, only model 4, which removes customer preferences from the analysis, exhibits any considerable change in the adjusted R squared with a value of 0.8990. This is lower than the remaining models which range from values of 0.9234 to 0.9399. In general, this is positive as it suggests that the initial analysis is not heavily reliant on an individual factor. In addition, the majority of variables provide consistent results throughout models 1 to 6 and behave in the same way as the coefficients in the initial regression. For instance, all of the results for the fuel and electricity index, tax breaks, recycling, range of electric vehicles, education, number of public chargers, income index and unemployment match the initial regression. Many of these results are also strongly statistically significant.

However, these robustness checks also provide unexpected results. For example, some of the coefficients for the initial cost of vehicles act against the literature and initial results. This is most evident in model 4, which is statistically significant at the 1% level. One explanation for this is the presence of government incentives, which as already discussed, may distort some early data for this variable as subsidies were initially large to encourage early adopters. Nonetheless, the data consistently matches the literature and argues that subsidies have a positive impact on ZEV adoption rates apart from model 4. Hence, it is possible that there is a clash between the two variables that has skewed the data slightly and led to these unexpected results. Therefore, these robustness checks provide largely positive results.

5 Policy Implications

These results provide clarity on the policies that the UK Government should use to ensure that their 2035 deadline is met. As Figure 3 demonstrates, the UK Government has set ambitious annual targets for adoption rates, anticipating large continuous growth. However, 12 years is a long time and economic shocks, which can massively impact causal factors such as income and unemployment, are possible. This may lead to stagnant periods of growth in ZEV adoption rates and annual targets not being met. Hence, the UK Government may be required to intervene to boost ZEV adoption rates over time.

Figure 3: Annual ZEV adoption rates with target growth rates until 2035

Source: Department for Transport (2023c) and Department for Transport (2023d)

Using the data analysis, the feasibility and effectiveness of specific policies on each variable can be examined. This is summarised in Table 5 with 3 key categories: insignificant, complementary and catalyst variables.

Table 5: Summary of viable policies that the UK Government could implement with results from model 1 in Section 4.1

Description	Variables	(1) OLS with ln(ZEV)
Insignificant	Tax breaks (£)	-0.0052*** (0.0010)
	Recycling (1,000 kg)	-0.0001 (0.0012)
Complementary	Relative prices of electric vehicles	-0.0487 (0.4200)
	Subsidies on upfront cost (£)	0.0004** (0.0002)
	Range of electric vehicles (miles)	0.0154*** (0.0018)
	Education (%)	0.1602** (0.0635)
	Income index	0.0340 (0.0344)
	Unemployment rate (%)	-0.3267*** (0.1015)
Catalyst	Fuel and electricity index difference	0.0103** (0.0046)
	Number of public chargers (1,000s)	0.0962*** (0.0359)
	R Square	0.9442
	Adjusted R Square	0.9394
	Observations	126
	Standard error in parentheses	
	Statistical significance: * = p < 0.1, ** = p < 0.05, *** = p < 0.01	

5.1. Insignificant variables

The results of the analysis argue that tax breaks and recycling levels are ineffective at increasing ZEV adoption rates. Therefore, it is difficult to suggest that they should be key policy considerations for the UK Government.

However, given the success of major tax breaks in countries such as Norway, this should not be ignored completely, and future research should analyse this variable further. Furthermore, tax breaks in the UK have been relatively small (maximum level of £750), so the analysis of this variable is limited as other policies and variables have a much greater magnitude across this time period. In addition, there should be a key effort to develop and quantify variables such as environmental morality, which are often omitted in previous literature.

However, this is difficult to account for as a key simplification would be to assume that all consumers are rational and behave in the same way. However, this is not true in reality and two individuals could have the same care for the environment but make different purchasing decisions. For instance, one individual may feel that by purchasing a ZEV they have made a huge effort to combat the climate crisis, and as a result may neglect smaller tasks that will help to reduce their carbon footprint such as recycling regularly. By comparison, another individual may supplement not purchasing a ZEV by being particularly diligent in completing all of the smaller tasks that can reduce their carbon footprint. Individuals may also make other environmental purchases, such as solar panels for their home, instead of purchasing a ZEV. Therefore, although factors such as environmental morality are extremely important to consider, they may not have a direct impact on ZEV sales.

5.2. Complementary variables

Furthermore, many variables are impactful according to the data but may be difficult for the UK Government to significantly influence.

For instance, the UK Government may struggle to affect the relative price or range of vehicles. In both cases this intervention would likely involve large investments in technology, which has no guarantee of producing major changes. Furthermore, the data provided results which largely underestimate the impact of the relative price of vehicles compared to what is expected based on the literature. However, this is partly due to the magnitude of ZEV subsidies that were implemented by the UK Government to encourage early adoption (£5,000 in 2013 compared to £0 in 2023). In addition, the range of vehicles are now at a point which much more resembles the range of equivalent petrol and diesel vehicles. For example, Table 3 established that the average range of ZEVs was initially 84 miles in 2013 but was 247 miles by 2023. Hence, future improvements to the range of ZEVs may have also have less of an impact than the data anticipates that they will. Furthermore, these policies are long-term investments. Therefore, if the UK Government is intent

on reaching this 2035 deadline, they may not be viable.

In addition, subsidies may not be a preferred policy. Approximately 2 million new vehicles are registered every year in the UK (Department for Transport, 2023c). Hence, even a small subsidy of £1,000 would currently cost the UK Government around £400m to fund in a single year with adoption rates at approximately 20% (Department for Transport, 2023c). This cost would also increase over time as adoption rates rise. Therefore, although subsidies can be impactful, it is far more rational to use this policy at the early stages of adoption, as the UK has done, and to focus on other policies as adoption rates improve. Furthermore, the UK Government have committed huge funds to policies with long-term benefits such as increasing the number of public ZEV chargers. This will cost them £1.6 billion to raise this figure from approximately 50,000 to 300,000 by 2030 (Department for Transport, 2022c). These policies are more beneficial as ZEV chargers are a necessary spend in the future as the ZEV market increases. By comparison, subsidies will only have a short-term benefit of boosting ZEV adoption rates. However, aggressive government incentives have been effective in other countries, so this could still be considered if vast change was required.

Education policies could also be effective but are unlikely to lead to massive rises in ZEV adoption rates. Much of the population are already aware of the benefits of driving an electric vehicle compared to other vehicles so an education scheme would be unlikely to change this dramatically. Furthermore, much of the change in awareness around ZEVs is natural and develops over time as these vehicles become more common on the road (Krishna, 2021). Hence, an education policy raising awareness about the benefits of ZEVs and how to use them is unlikely to lead to any major change. Nonetheless, this policy should be encouraged if it could be implemented at a low cost.

Moreover, both the income index and unemployment level are difficult to massively influence. Obviously, the UK Government targets high levels of income per capita and low unemployment rates. However, this is difficult to change dramatically in the short-term given that these variables are

vulnerable to economic cycles and shocks (Denis and Kannan, 2013). Unemployment rates have not gone below 3.5% in the last 10 years as demonstrated by Table 3. Hence, it is challenging for the UK Government to reduce unemployment rates significantly below the June 2023 level of 4.3%. Furthermore, the only potentially viable short-term solution to combat the issue of income levels without reducing the price of ZEVs is to change the way that ZEVs are purchased. For instance, an accessible credit scheme to purchase ZEVs. However, this was challenging to quantify in this study and should be examined by other studies in more detail.

This analysis does not mean that these factors should be completely disregarded, but they are more likely to be complementary to other key policies rather than the driving force for increasing ZEV adoption rates.

5.3. Catalyst variables

From the data and analysis, it becomes clear that there are two key policies that the UK Government should implement to improve ZEV adoption rates.

Firstly, increasing the difference between the fuel and electricity index by raising the level of taxation on fuel prices could be extremely effective, given that both the data and literature suggested that consumers are fairly responsive to these price changes. This is more realistic and less expensive than subsidising electricity prices. Increasing taxation on petrol and diesel prices by 1 pence per litre would currently generate an additional revenue of approximately £450m for the UK Government (Office for Budget Responsibility, 2023). Hence, this additional tax revenue could fund other policies such as increasing the number of ZEV chargers. However, setting this tax level too high may negatively impact the disposable income of consumers, which could result in some being unable to afford ZEVs, particularly if there is not an adequate financing or credit scheme.

Finally, the supply of ZEV chargers appears to be the key stumbling block that could prevent the UK Government from reaching their targets. Countries such as Norway have demonstrated that adequate and accessible charging infrastructure for the whole population, provides a great platform for ZEV adoption rates to consistently rise rapidly over time. Moreover, the data argues that even a small increase in the number of chargers (1,000) can generate large increases in adoption rates (9.62% rise). Hence, constructing an adequate national ZEV charging infrastructure is paramount to ensure that all new vehicles that are registered are ZEVs by 2035. Therefore, it is encouraging that the UK Government has already committed to spending £1.6 billion on ZEV chargers until 2030, as it is clearly something that it intends to take very seriously (Department for Transport, 2022c).

6 Conclusion

Overall, the signs are encouraging, and the UK Government appears to be in a fairly strong position to reach its 2035 target to have all new vehicles registered be ZEVs. However, there is a long way to go, and intervention may be necessary should adoption rates fall below target levels.

In general, the data and analysis leads to the conclusion that the relationship between fuel and electricity prices, as well as the supply of public ZEV chargers can be the catalysts for improving ZEV adoption rates. In particular, the supply of public ZEV chargers should be the key focus for the UK Government as this will have the greatest long-term impact on adoption rates. Without this many consumers may not have the confidence to effectively use and charge a ZEV efficiently which would restrict ZEV sales. Increasing taxation on fuel prices could also be hugely important to accelerate the rise in ZEV adoption rates and potentially even increase the number of public ZEV chargers. However, this tax increase needs to be selected carefully to ensure that it does not prevent consumers from affording ZEVs altogether.

Furthermore, the data argues that other factors such as the initial cost of vehicles, government incentives, customer preferences and income also have causal impacts on ZEV adoption rates in the UK. However, in each of these cases it can be challenging, expensive or ineffective for the UK Government to implement policies on these factors in isolation. Nonetheless, many of these potential policies could be successful if they were used to complement more productive policies such as increasing taxation on fuel prices or the number of public ZEV chargers. In particular, government incentives, including subsidies and tax breaks, should be examined in more detail as even though the data does not suggest that these are crucial, they have clearly been successful in other countries and the literature supports this.

This study could be improved and developed upon with a variety of future research. Firstly, there are minimal studies on this topic in the UK, so this

paper has added to that. However, additional research on the UK could be extremely impactful. For instance, future research could focus on how ZEV adoption rates differ and are affected regionally, as this could allow for supplementary analysis on other UK Government schemes, such as the introduction of low emission zones. Furthermore, future studies should analyse new variables as well as the existing ones that have been discussed in this study. For example, examining the effect of financing and credit schemes. Finally, a key piece of analysis that would be particularly insightful is attempting to quantify the non-financial factors that could impact ZEV adoption rates. This could include variables such as environmental morality, information gaps and the supply of ZEVs in the UK.

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